

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF DIDACTIC ABILITY TO STUDENTS.

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Abstract: the problem of professional adaptation and the formation of teachers is covered in the work. The specific of the training of future teachers in the university that is focused on the development of pedagogical abilities is described. On the basis of the personal and activity approach, the examples of assignments are presented in connection with various groups of pedagogical abilities.

Keywords: pedagogical abilities, personal approach, activity approach, didactic abilities, speech abilities, academic abilities, perceptual abilities, communicative abilities, organizational abilities

Main part: At the present stage of development of vocational education, it remains actual problem of systemic formation of pedagogical abilities future teachers. According to statistics, the number of graduates who have received a teaching diploma is second only to the number of lawyers and doctors. Despite to the fact that in recent years there has been an influx of young teachers (according to the Minister of Education and Science of Russia O.Yu. Vasilyeva, in the 2017 academic year year in 59 regions of Russia their influx amounted to 5–10%) the need of educational institutions for specialists remains quite high. It is important to emphasize also the difficulties of adaptation and professional development of young teachers, since the process of formation and professional development significant qualities is complex and depends on a combination of factors and conditions of the educational process. In our opinion, it is necessary to solve the identified problem by orienting students of a pedagogical university to understanding, accepting and exploring the beauty and multifunctionality of pedagogical activity. WITH on the one hand, presupposing scientific, methodological and psychological-pedagogical knowledge, focus on creative solutions to professional problems with another, readiness for self-knowledge, self-improvement, accumulation experience, painstaking, daily work requiring attention to detail, observation and detailed analysis. Understanding and acceptance of the teaching profession by future teachers, is largely determined by the purposeful work of university teachers to develop their teaching abilities throughout their education. Pedagogical abilities are classified as special abilities and are most often defined as a combination of such individual psychological characteristics and professionally significant qualities of a teacher, which ensure the achievement of high results in teaching activities. According to the classification of V.A. Krutetsky's group of pedagogical abilities includes: didactic, speech, academic, perceptual, communicative and organizational abilities.

While analysing intellectual component of RC of the future teacher we'd like to say that according to M. A. Kholodnaya - the author of the fundamental investigation of the intellect psychology (Kholodnaya, 2002) there is no general approach when defining the concept of "intellect", which is defined by the researchers as a general ability of an individual to consciously set his/her thinking in accordance with the appearing requirements, intellectual adaptation to the new conditions of life (V. Stern); as a combined and general ability of individuals to act adequately, think logically and interact with the life realia (D. Veksler); as an ability to process information under which one understands as the whole range of human perception (P. Gilford). Thus, we can base on the fact that the intellect is an ability of a person to perform cognitive processes and solve problematic tasks including setting previously unknown tasks. As we have already pointed out, an intellectual component of RC is a total of interconnected knowledge which in its turn can be

considered as a result of the mental and practical activity of a human which is represented by the system of empiric facts, theoretical concepts, scientific laws and theories. The purpose of the knowledge is the organisation of the cognitive process and explanation of the processes and events occurring in the surrounding world. While analysing an intellectual component of the RC it is necessary to define both the types of knowledge acquired by the future teacher while forming RC and methods of cognition applied for this. The scope of knowledge acquired by a human has a tendency to constantly increase, which depends on the activity of a human. Human intellect can be changed with the course of time. It is influenced both by the internal (e.g. good memory, creative activity) and external factors. The latter in their turn it can both accelerates and slows down. The factors which accelerate the intellectual development are stimulation, encouragement, ambition, recognition by the society, discretion etc.; the slowing once are punishment, accusation, conviction, absence or lack of ambition etc. The degree of RC formation depends directly on the intellectual level of a future teacher. Due to this fact it is necessary to take into account the above mentioned factors when stimulating a cognitive process. According to the data of M. F. Shklyar we can point out the following forms of cognition: empiric and creative. These forms of cognition do not oppose but mutually complete each other since the spheres of their use often meet. (Shklyar, 2012). The empiric form of cognition is primary, it is initially present in any practical human activity. Historically this form of cognition supplied a human with all the necessary sum of knowledge in different spheres of his/her activity up to the appearance of special ways of cognition. The specific nature of the empiric form of cognition is in the absence of the systematic nature and goal as well as in the unconscious use of empiric methods of research. In the case of empiric cognition the latter often occurs intuitively, partially with the support of the primary knowledge of the subject of research. Due to this fact one should include the presence of the intuitive knowledge of use of the empiric methods of research and primary knowledge in the sphere of research in the RC component.

Conclusion: In conclusion of the research we should note that students' RC is a component of the general professional pedagogical culture. The formation of RC should be based on the future teachers' performing of the scientific-investigative work. The process of the students' intellect development within the framework of RC gives the opportunity to define the most effective methods of solving today's contradictions between the changes in the society and the level of the future teacher's readiness for the professional activity; between the constant increase of the amount of information and abilities of its perception; between the state demand for the teachers with the formed RC and insufficient working out of this problem in theory and practice.

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